

LC-BASED AMINO ACID RESEARCH IN EPILEPSY: A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS (2010–2025)

Demet Kablan^{1*}, Meriç Emre Bostancı²

Keywords

Bibliometric analysis,

VOSviewer,

Amino acids,

Epilepsy,

Liquid chromatograph (LC)

ABSTRACT

Epilepsy is a chronic neurological disorder characterized by recurrent seizures, affecting millions of people worldwide. This study aims to provide a comprehensive bibliometric and visual analysis in order to examine the current trends and research patterns of research into amino acids in the field of epilepsy. The publications were obtained from the Web of Science (WoS) database and bibliometric analyses were carried out using VOSviewer software, bibliometrix R package and Biblioshiny web tool. The analysis is limited to original articles and review articles published between 2010 and 2025. After applying document type and English language restrictions, the analysis was carried out on a total of 106 articles published by institutions in 38 different countries. In order to determine the thematic structure of the research area, keyword co-occurrence analysis was performed based on author keywords. The minimum number of times a keyword is seen is set at three. In addition, overlay visualization analysis was applied to reveal temporal trends in the research area and to identify emerging topics. A country collaboration network analysis was also carried out to evaluate scientific cooperation between countries. The countries with the highest number of publications are the USA, Japan, Brazil and France. Keyword co-occurrence analysis revealed that the most frequently used keywords included “epilepsy”, “metabolomics”, “amino acids”, “glutamate”, “biomarker”, and “mass spectrometry”. In addition, the fact that topics such as “epileptogenesis” and “biomarkers,” which have recently come to the forefront, have begun to attract increasing attention indicates a shift toward more comprehensive and application-oriented research approaches. The findings reveal the development of research on amino acids in the field of epilepsy and provide a general scientific framework for future studies in this field.

INTRODUCTION

Epilepsy is a chronic neurological disorder characterized by recurrent seizures, affecting millions of people worldwide. The pathophysiology of epilepsy is quite complex and involves the interaction of genetic, molecular and metabolic mechanisms. Recent studies show that neurotransmitter balance and amino acid metabolism play an important role in the development of epilepsy and seizure formation^{1,2}. Glutamate, gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) and other amino acids play critical roles in the regulation of excitatory and inhibitory neurotransmission in the central nervous system. Amino acids that function as excitatory and inhibitory neurotransmitters, as well as various amino acid derivatives involved in metabolic pathways, are also important components of the biochemical networks associated with the epileptic process^{3,4}.

The study of amino acids in the context of epilepsy has undergone a significant transformation in parallel with the developments in analytical technologies. While methods that allowed the measurement of a limited number of analytes were used in the early studies, with the widespread use of liquid chromatography (LC)-based techniques, especially liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS), more sensitive, selective and multiple analyte measurements have become possible⁵. This technological advancement has expanded the methodological framework of the field, enabling the analysis of not only individual amino acids but also broad metabolic profiles⁶. Although there are many studies examining the relationship between epilepsy and amino acids, the thematic distribution, methodological orientations and development of these studies over time have not been systematically evaluated. The studies available in the literature mostly focus on experimental or clinical results; however, the lack of a holistic bibliometric analysis revealing the conceptual structure and research trends of the field draws attention. Bibliometric studies provide important information about the general structure of the literature by revealing the numerical distribution, thematic structures, and research collaborations of publications in a specific research field^{7,8}.

Volume: 4

Issue: 2

Page: 125–130

Received: 26.04.2026

Accepted: 01.06.2026

Available online: 30.06.2026

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.20266927

1*- Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Medicine, Sivas Cumhuriyet University, Sivas, Turkey, demetekablan@gmail.com, ORCID: 0000-0002-3988-4603

2- Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Medicine, Sivas Cumhuriyet University, Sivas, Turkey, drmericembostanci@gmail.com, ORCID:0000-0002-0429-9834

The aim of this study is to reveal research trends, thematic structure and international cooperation networks by performing a bibliometric analysis of LC-based amino acid research in the field of epilepsy. In this context, the thematic structure and temporal evolution of amino acid research carried out using LC-based methods in the field of epilepsy between 2010 and 2025 were systematically analyzed through bibliometric methods in the current study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data Collection and Search Strategy

The data for this bibliometric study was retrieved from the Web of Science (WoS) Core Collection database on March 5, 2026. Studies published after this date were not included in the analysis. The research was carried out with the aim of identifying publications focused on epilepsy and amino acid research using analytical techniques based on liquid chromatography. As a search query, it was created using the Topic field (TS) and included the following terms: (epilepsy OR seizure) AND ("amino acid" OR "amino acid profiling") and ("liquid chromatography" or "LC-MS/MS").

Search was limited to publications published between 2010 and 2025 only. Only original research articles and review articles written in English were included. Records that met these criteria were exported as a Plain Text File (.txt) using the "Full Record and Cited References" option of the WoS database.

Bibliometric Analysis

As a result of the search query, 212 records were identified. Inclusion criteria 106 publications published between 2010 and 2025 were excluded after applying original articles and review articles, limited document type and English language restriction. The remaining 106 publications were included in the bibliometric analyses. No manual screening was performed, and all records that met the predefined inclusion criteria were analyzed.

Bibliometric analyses were performed using VOSviewer software (biblioshiny 4.1.4, a web interface for the bibliometrix R package, and VOSviewer 1.6.20 software)^{9,10}. In order to determine the thematic structure of the research area, keyword commonality analysis was performed based on the keywords of the authors. The minimum number of encounters for a keyword is set to three. Network visualization maps were created to identify thematic clusters.

Visualization analysis was performed on top of each other to assess the temporal evolution of the research subjects. In this analysis, keywords are color-coded based on their average publication year.

In addition, a country-level co-authorship analysis was conducted to examine patterns of international cooperation. Countries with at least five publications were included in the analysis. A full count method was applied to calculate co-authorship links (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Flow chart of study selection process.

RESULTS

Broadcast Features

A total of 212 records were initially detected through the Web of Science Core Collection database. 106 records were excluded after applying the English language, limited to document-type articles and review articles, with predefined

inclusion criteria between 2010 and 2025. The remaining 106 publications were included in the bibliometric analysis.

The distribution of publications over time has shown a gradual increase in research output, especially after 2016, indicating the growing interest in LC-based amino acid research in the field of epilepsy (Table 1).

Table 1. General characteristics of the bibliometric dataset and analysis parameters.

Variable	Value
Total records identified	212
Records included in analysis	106
Time span	2010–2025
Keywords meeting minimum occurrence threshold (≥ 3)	21
Number of thematic clusters	6
Countries meeting publication threshold (≥ 5 documents)	6
Countries in the largest connected collaboration network	4

Keyword Coexistence Analysis

Keyword coexistence analysis was performed based on the authors' keywords and the minimum occurrence threshold was determined as three. A total of 21 keywords met this criterion and were included in the network visualization.

The most commonly used keyword was "mass spectrometry" (n = 9), followed by "amino acids" (n = 6) and "cerebrospinal fluid" (n = 6). The term "glutamate" appeared in four publications; "temporal lobe epilepsy" and "antiepileptic drugs" were used in four and three publications, respectively.

The network visualization revealed six distinct thematic clusters that represent the conceptual structure of the research area. These clusters included: (i) clinical biomarker and cerebrospinal fluid-related studies; (ii) experimental research centered on amino acid metabolism and glutamate; (iii) epileptogenesis and proteomics-oriented research; (iv) studies based on the animal model; (v) analytical and pharmacological approaches; and (vi) methodologies based on metabolomics and nuclear magnetic resonance (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Network visualization of keyword co-occurrence analysis showing six thematic clusters in LC-based amino acid research in epilepsy (minimum occurrence = 3)

Temporal Trend Analysis

Visualization analysis showed a temporal shift over the research focus. While previous publications have mainly been focused on glutamate and traditional analytical approaches, recent studies have seen an emphasis on metabolomics and advanced mass spectrometry-based techniques (Figure 3).

In addition, the fact that topics such as “epileptogenesis” and “biomarkers,” which have recently come to the forefront, have begun to attract increasing attention indicates a shift toward more comprehensive and application-oriented research approaches.

Figure 3. Overlay visualization of keyword co-occurrence analysis illustrating the temporal evolution of research topics in LC-based amino acid research in epilepsy. Node colors represent the average publication year (blue: earlier publications; yellow: more recent publications).

Country Collaboration Analysis

Although there were 38 countries that conducted the study in the analysis, the country-level co-authorship analysis was carried out with a threshold of at least five publications per country. As a result, four countries met the network criteria and were included in the cooperation network.

The United States has emerged as the leading contributor and central node in the collaboration network. Japan, France, and Brazil were also identified as active contributors. The cooperation map showed that research activities were concentrated in a limited number of countries, with the United States showing the strongest cooperation links (Figure 4)

Figure 4: Country Collaboration Analysis

DISCUSSION

In our study, the bibliometric profile of amino acid research based on liquid chromatography in epilepsy was examined. Articles and reviews published between 2010 and 2025 were included in the study, revealing the thematic structure, temporal trends, and international cooperation patterns of the research area. Six different thematic clusters were identified in the keyword cooccurrence analysis, which showed that amino acid research in epilepsy has gained a multidisciplinary structure. Temporal analysis revealed that while the research focus was on glutamate and experimental models in the early stages, it has turned to metabolomics approaches and epileptogenesis processes in recent years. Furthermore, country-level co-authorship analysis has shown that research activities are concentrated around a limited number of countries, with the United States playing a central role in the collaborative network.

Keyword coexistence analysis, which was carried out to reveal the thematic structure of the research area, showed that epilepsy and amino acid research is clustered around different research focuses. The six thematic clusters obtained reveal that this field is a multifaceted field of research, encompassing both experimental and clinical dimensions. It is noteworthy that some clusters represent experimental studies based on glutamate metabolism and animal models¹, while other clusters include cerebrospinal fluid and biomarker-focused clinical trials¹¹. In addition, it has been observed that studies based on metabolomics approaches and advanced analytical techniques¹² constitute a separate thematic area. This shows that amino acid metabolism in epilepsy research has begun to be addressed not only at the neurotransmitter level, but also at the level of metabolic networks and systems.

Temporal trend analysis revealed that research subjects showed a significant change over time. Overlay visualization results show that early studies mainly focused on experimental approaches based on glutamate and animal models, while recent studies have focused on metabolomics approaches, advanced mass spectrometry techniques, and epileptogenesis processes¹³. The prominence of the concept of epileptogenesis in recent years indicates that there is a growing interest in understanding not only seizures but also the development process of the disease and the underlying molecular mechanisms in epilepsy research. This shows that amino acid studies in epilepsy research have evolved from studies at the

individual neurotransmitter level to system-level approaches in which metabolic networks and the mechanisms of disease formation are considered more holistically. In particular, the increasing presence of metabolomics approaches in the field of research¹⁴ suggests that advanced analytical technologies allow for a more comprehensive study of the biochemical basis of epilepsy.

A country-level co-authorship analysis shows that the international cooperation network in epilepsy and amino acid research is concentrated around specific countries. According to the results of the analysis, the United States is in a central position in the cooperation network and shows strong connections with other countries. Japan, France and Brazil have also stood out as important contributors to the field of research. However, the concentration of the resulting cooperation network among a limited number of countries shows that international cooperation in epilepsy and amino acid research is shaped around a limited core research network. We think that expanding international research networks and establishing stronger collaborations between different research centers may contribute to the development of studies on amino acid metabolism in epilepsy.

This study has some limitations. First of all, the analyzes were limited to publications indexed in the Web of Science Core Collection database and studies in other databases were not included in the analysis. In addition, the evaluation of articles and reviews published only in English may have caused some regional studies to be excluded from the analysis. Despite this, this study provides an overview of the literature by revealing the thematic structure, methodological development and research trends of research on amino acid metabolism in the field of epilepsy.

CONCLUSION

This study is one of a limited number of bibliometric analyses focusing on amino acid research in the field of epilepsy. In this study, the sources, countries, authors, keywords, and thematic structures of articles on epilepsy and amino acids published between 2010 and 2025 were analyzed. In addition, research trends in the literature on the subject were also revealed. The findings show that studies on amino acid metabolism in the field of epilepsy have attracted increasing attention in recent years.

We think that future studies will contribute to the development of the field by performing more comprehensive bibliometric analyzes including different databases and examining the relationships between metabolomics approaches and epileptogenesis processes in more detail.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest in this work.

Ethical Approval Statement

Ethics committee approval is not required as there is no human or animal research.

Acknowledgements: Sivas Cumhuriyet University

REFERENCES

1. Chen TS, Huang TH, Lai MC, Huang CW. The role of glutamate receptors in epilepsy. *Biomedicines*. 2023;11(3):783.
2. Barker-Haliski M, White HS. Glutamatergic mechanisms associated with seizures and epilepsy. *Cold Spring Harb Perspect Med*. 2015;5(8):a022863.
3. Sarlo GL, Holton KF. Brain concentrations of glutamate and GABA in human epilepsy: A review. *Seizure*. 2021;91:213-227.
4. Lai W, Du D, Chen L. Metabolomics provides novel insights into epilepsy diagnosis and treatment: a review. *Neurochem Res*. 2022;47(4):844-859.
5. Psychogios N, Hau DD, Peng J, Guo AC, Mandal R, Bouatra S, et al. The human serum metabolome. *PLoS One*. 2011;6(2):e16957.
6. Wishart DS. Emerging applications of metabolomics in drug discovery and precision medicine. *Nat Rev Drug Discov*. 2016;15(7):473-484.
7. Donthu N, Kumar S, Mukherjee D, Pandey N, Lim WM. How to conduct a bibliometric analysis: An overview and guidelines. *J Bus Res*. 2021;133:285-296.
8. Lim WM, Kumar S. Guidelines for interpreting the results of bibliometric analysis: A sensemaking approach. *Glob Bus Organ Excell*. 2024;43(2):17-26.
9. Arruda H, Silva ER, Lessa M, Proenca D Jr, Bartholo R. Resource review. *J Med Libr Assoc*. 2022;110(3):392-395.
10. Aria M, Cuccurullo C. bibliometrix: An R-tool for comprehensive science mapping analysis. *J Informetr*. 2017;11(4):959-975.
11. Eriksson AS, O'Connor WT. Analysis of CSF amino acids in young patients with generalised refractory epilepsy during an add-on study with lamotrigine. *Epilepsy Res*. 1999;34(1):75-83.
12. Eid T. Harnessing metabolomics to advance epilepsy research. *Epilepsy Curr*. 2022;22(2):123-129.
13. Kang W, Han Q, Chen M, Xue L, Zhao Z, Liu R, et al. Alterations in serum metabolomics predict drug-resistant epilepsy. *Sci Rep*. 2025.
14. Chojnowski K, Opielka M, Urbanowicz K, Zawadzka M, Wangin K, Smoleński RT, Mazurkiewicz-Beldzińska M. Untargeted metabolomics reveals key metabolic alterations in pediatric epilepsy with insights into tryptophan metabolism and the gut-brain axis. *Sci Rep*. 2025;15(1):15262.